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ABSTRACT

Agricultural insurance represents one of the key mechanisms ensuring the sustainable development of agriculture and the financial stability of farmers. In Georgia, the state-subsidized agricultural insurance program has been in operation since 2014 and covers risks such as hail, storms, excessive precipitation, and early autumn frost. The state-subsidized program implemented since 2014 has made a significant contribution to the establishment of a risk management system in the sector and to raising farmers' awareness.

However, the agricultural insurance system is still in a stage of development and requires further improvement at the institutional, technical, and organizational levels. The main challenges remain the low coverage of the program, the insufficient number of meteorological stations, and the geographical concentration of insured land plots in high-risk regions. This trend creates the risk of adverse selection and limits the even nationwide dissemination of the agricultural insurance program.

Overcoming these challenges requires close cooperation between the public and private sectors, the harmonization of agricultural insurance policy and practice, the introduction of a unified damage assessment methodology, and the strengthening of farmer awareness and information. In addition, it is advisable to develop new insurance products and financial incentives, taking regional specificities into account, which would encourage the involvement of small and medium-sized farmers in low-risk regions as well.

Such an approach will contribute to the comprehensive development of the agricultural insurance system, ensure the economic security of farmers, and enhance the competitiveness of the agricultural sector, which ultimately constitutes a foundation for the country's economic sustainability.

Keywords: risk, insurance, agricultural insurance, agriculture, state, private sector.

Human daily life and activities continuously involve various types of risks and the probability of unforeseen events. Despite the modern achievements in the development of science and technology, there still exist circumstances that pose serious challenges to individuals. Among these, natural disasters are particularly noteworthy, as they often cause significant damage and can substantially affect a person's socio-economic condition. Under such conditions, the need for protective mechanisms that ensure the continuation of life with minimal losses and the maintenance of economic stability becomes increasingly important.

Insurance represents one of the most widespread and effective financial instruments for risk management. Agricultural insurance enables farmers to protect their crops against various risks and to avoid financial losses.

In Georgia, a subsidized agricultural insurance program based on cooperation between the public and private sectors has been in operation since 2014 and aims to ensure farmers' financial stability and the sustainability of agriculture.

Due to the specific geographical location of Georgia's territory and its complex relief, various types of natural hydrometeorological processes frequently occur, among which hail is particularly significant. In this regard, the Kakheti region stands out, where hail often causes damage to the region. The damage caused by hail amounts to millions of GEL annually. Accordingly, it is natural that among the named risks covered under the agricultural insurance program, hail represents one of the most important types of coverage. It should be noted that more than half of the insured plots are concentrated in the Kakheti region. According to

2024 data, within the framework of the agricultural insurance program, 79% of insured land plots are insured in Kakheti, while 69% of insured plots are vineyards.

Within the framework of the program, insurance coverage, in addition to hail, includes such major risks as storms, excessive precipitation, and early autumn frost (only for citrus crops).

Based on the program's outcomes, its conditions are refined and clarified, and changes are implemented almost every year. The definition of the deductible (franchise) has been clarified; a unified damage assessment standard (for certain crops) has been developed for all insurance companies participating in the project; reporting procedures and deadlines have been improved; normative yields, tariffs, and the co-financing percentage have been reviewed and specified; and three-year insurance for perennial crops has become possible. In addition, continuous video recording and audio recording using body-worn cameras during the process of describing an insured event have been made mandatory.

Despite the progress achieved, the agricultural insurance system continues to face significant challenges. Although the share of agricultural insurance in the insurance market has been increasing from year to year, it remains very small and in 2024 accounted for only 1.57% of the total insurance market.

Low coverage remains one of the main challenges of Georgia's agricultural insurance system and significantly limits the effectiveness of the program. Despite the fact that the state-subsidized agricultural insurance program has been operating since 2014 and provides farmers with the opportunity to protect their crops against various types of risks, its geographical and sectorial coverage remains limited. The number of insured

plots constitutes only a small share of the country's total agricultural land, indicating both a lack of information and low farmer motivation to participate in the program. One of the reasons for low coverage is the insufficient meteorological infrastructure—specifically, the limited number of meteorological stations—and issues related to the accuracy of the data obtained from

them. Accurate meteorological data form the foundation of the agricultural insurance system, as damage assessment directly depends on such data. From the launch of the program through 2024, the number of insured plots is distributed as follows.

Diagram №1.

The amendment implemented in 2018, according to which only land plots registered with the National Agency of Public Registry were eligible for insurance,

resulted in a 45% decrease in the number of insured land plots.

Diagram №2.

Adverse selection remains a significant challenge. One of the most illustrative examples of adverse selection in Georgia's agricultural insurance program is the uneven geographical distribution of insured plots. According to available data, more than half of the insured plots are concentrated in only three regions—Kakheti, Shida Kartli, and Kvemo Kartli—out of Georgia's 12 regions. This fact clearly indicates that interest in agricultural insurance is predominantly expressed by farmers operating in high-risk areas, where hail, strong winds, and excessive precipitation are frequent and the probability of crop damage is high. Consequently, in lower-risk regions, such as Imereti, farmers' interest in

insurance is significantly lower, which disrupts the spatial balance of the program and increases the risk of adverse selection. This trend underscores the need for the state and the private sector, through close cooperation, to develop additional incentives and mechanisms that would encourage farmers in low-risk regions to participate in the agricultural insurance system as well, thereby ensuring geographical diversification of the program and promoting the sustainable development of the sector.

Since the inception of the program and up to 2024, insurance companies have compensated losses totaling over 92 million lari, while aggregate gross premiums during the same period exceeded 135 million lari.

Diagram №3.

Agricultural insurance in Georgia represents one of the key mechanisms for ensuring the sustainable development of agriculture, the financial stability of farmers, and social protection. The agricultural insurance program, introduced by the state in 2014, has played a significant role in establishing a risk management system within the agricultural sector and raising farmers' awareness. Despite the results achieved, the program is still in a developmental stage and requires improvement at administrative, technical, and institutional levels. One of the main challenges remains low coverage and the limited number of meteorological stations. In addition, insured plots are primarily concentrated in a few high-risk regions, particularly Kakheti, where hail and other natural disasters are frequent. Such geographical imbalance has increased the risk of adverse selection—farmers in low-risk regions show less interest in insurance, which disrupts the equitable and effective distribution of the program nationwide. In this context, it is advisable, taking regional specificities into account, to develop new insurance products and mechanisms, which requires close cooperation between the public and private sectors. It also necessitates strengthening informational, technological, and financial mechanisms. Only through these measures will it be possible

to enhance the agricultural insurance system, ensure farmers' economic protection, and increase the competitiveness of the agricultural sector in the face of global climatic and economic changes, which, ultimately, forms the foundation for the country's economic sustainability.

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